

GOOD PRACTICES IN SUSTAINABILITY APPLIEDUS BUILDINGS THAT USES TECHNOLOGY BIM

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ABSTRACT

The growing demand for more sustainable buildings, efficiency in the execution of civil construction projects give rise to the relevance of making due use of technology in increasing works. Building Information Modeling (BIM) creates and uses the compressed computational data of a building project, this parametric knowledge is common in the work for risk management, document formulation, performance anticipation, cost estimation, problem solving and idealization. The problem question of the work was: “How can civil construction companies apply strategies through the BIM tool to reduce environmental impacts in the construction of buildings?”. The following general objective is to analyze the BIM tool applied to sustainability in the construction of buildings. In this work, it was a bibliographical review. To define the work step by step, we used Bryman's recommendation (2008), which advises starting by understanding the topic, choosing information sources, data collection, data analysis, interpretation and proposal, and finally , result. Finally, it is worth highlighting that the use of BIM should not be considered a simple method of adopting a development model, but rather it is a multidisciplinary tool intended to correlate and enhance complex sectors in the design of sustainable engineering projects.

Keywords: Project, Sustainability, Construction.

1 INTRODUCTION

With the increase in civil construction and consequently the increase in its environmental and social impact, the admission of appropriate measures responsibility social has become an increasingly important factor within companies construction civil. (SANTOS; BERTULINO; PFEIFER, 2010).

Civil construction is one of the areas that makes the most use of natural resources and This results in damage to the environment, and due to this fact, essential to search for means

more smart It is sustainable as O BIM, helpinglike this The minimize those impacts to the quite environment (SAINTS; BERTULINO; PFEIFER, 2010).

At the moment to the companies want to do part from the responsibility Social at which he has been quite discussed, It is that prove what no It is just ramp up, but alsoin demanding social well-being and better quality of life, the environment and culture (STEFANO *et al.*, 2003).

Based on this, the growing demand per buildings more sustainable, effectiveness in the execution of civil construction projects give rise to the relevance of makingproper use of technology in increment of construction. To the simulations carried out in environment virtual show potential at forecast in problems It is, per Therefore, in the conjecture of solutions, both environmental and management from the constructions (GOMES, LIMA, 2021).

The virtual coherence of data and the importance of undertakings are cunning at customization in projects, per adapt one vast multiplicity of resolutions, systematizing the conditions of users, the impacts of the work and Supports decision-making in the face of setbacks. The studies and analyzes of multiple Domains of the industry of engineering It is Construction are indispensable for the creation, assignment of parameters and systems what support to the sockets inclearances, as occurs in projects what use to the tools computational type BIM (MORORÓ *et al.*, 2016).

O *Building Information Modeling* (BIM) create It is employment you data compressed computing in one project in edification, that knowledge parametric is common in the work for risk direction, document formulation, performance anticipation, cost estimation, problem solving and idealization. BIM can also be accentuated as a modeling technologyconnected The one set in Law Suit what create, ponder and disseminate models for a project (construction of buildings and other civil engineering works), the which performs The interpretation of information in engineering It is your interactions, in manner advance It is without The precision in designs detailed (LINO, 2012).

Due to the what he was cited previously, O gift work, he has as purpose to analyze O BIM as tool for O development from the sustainability in the construction of buildings. Sustainability is currently a very important topic important for The society. Then, treats The spite of development in strategies with the purpose of reducing impacts caused to the environment. In this In this sense, many companies seek to adopt sustainability as a relevant factorfor the company. Not only to promote sustainability, but also to contribute to sustainable development, but to do so it is necessary to create strategies what seek reduce the impacts environmental.

Civil construction causes several impacts, including waste and debris, and the environmental impacts caused by the construction of a house, the speculation real estate what he can induce The construction in buildings in regions what nowere urbanistically designed to gain the number of people in a building, for example, thus causing more negative impacts on cities (SAINTS; BERTULINO; PFEIFER, 2010).

A construction sustainable It is The solution for to reach O development sustainable. From this mode, The sustainability at construction It is The satisfaction of needs from the population current without compromising O future (MARTINS, 2018).

The work is justified due to the fact that BIM represents a good tool at the combat to the impacts caused to the quite environment, for the useinadequate supply of natural and non-natural resources. Energy efficiency is nothing more of one form in conservation in energy, different of what if consider The economy.

A economy in energy Visa O goal in reduce you spending at the consumption, already The efficiencyenergetics consists of a practice that, in addition to conserving energy, can be favorable for O quite environment.

The research to be developed below will have the problem question: “How civil construction companies can apply strategies through the BIM tool to reduction of environmental impacts in the construction of buildings?” With the followinggoal general to analyze The tool BIM applied The sustainability at construction inbuildings.

2 METHODOLOGY

In this chapter it will be rush The methodology employee for The concretizationfrom the search. You artifices methodological in one search tend The explain what they gobe the activities developed to achieve it. In other words, the type research and method used. According to Rodrigues (2007, p. 2), “methodologyScientific is a set of approaches, techniques and processes used by science to formulate and solve problems of objective knowledge acquisition, in a manner systematic”.

In this work, a bibliographical review will be carried out. To define the stepstep by step, we used the recommendation of Bryman (2008), which advises start for the understanding of theme, choice in sources in information, collect in data,data analysis, interpretation and proposal, and finally, result. According to Yin (2001),file analysis is beneficial when trying to present the incidence or predominance in one phenomenon per quite in analytics Statistics.

The research will have an exploratory and descriptive character and, in order to achieve it, same it will be accomplished readings in articles It is books international It is national. To the source they were chosen due The your importance at the quite academic, writing, It is per congruence at the theme idealized for O work, containing information prominent for O development of result this work.

For implementation of study they were certain some criteria for research inclusion, such as: approach the concept and use of BIM and projects sustainable. A search at literature It is The selection of the articles he was carried out us months in May and June 2022, in the Google Scholar database, Scielo, considered O resource online with information related The engineering civil It is corresponding areas , using keywords as: "BIM", "engineering" It is "sustainable". Work produced up to 2021 was taken into account, starting from the period 2004.

3. RESULTS

3.1 A Sustainability It is your dimensions

Sustainability aims to transform the environment into a better place, more balanced, thus improving people's quality of life and making the healthier planet, and distinguish itself in unequal dimensions or aspects, which when included proceed at the development sustainable. In agreement with Brundtland *et al.*, (1987, sp), sustainable development is what ensures that will answer "to the needs of gift without compromise The capacity in to the generations future attend also Yours...".

In agreement with Oak (2009), for to be considered development sustainable it is necessary to be responsible with the amount of use of resources natural resources, that is, it is necessary to make only a rational use of natural resources natural resources that are available to be used, so it is possible to understand the sociocultural, political, aesthetic and other issues. The link and dependence between the dimensions of sustainability is what causes the construction sustainable, where he divides sustainability into 3 groups, which can also be called of three dimensions from the sustainability: economical, environmental It is sociocultural. It can be concluded that the way in which one builds, designs and acts in improvement in one constructions influencing at the use of the resources natural It is at health from the population and of planet (OAK, 2009).

Second Librelotto (2005), The extension Social as The what he does mention The social responsibility and people management, the environmental dimension such as that worries with The precaution of ecosystems It is The decrease in conflicts It is damage to quite environment,

It is The extension economic what pay The response financial of the investments to the patented, community It is others related to the process.

Figure 1 - Construction Sustainable

Source: Adapted in Oak, 2009

3.2 Building Information Modeling – BIM

O Building Information Modeling (BIM), at Language Portuguese means “Building Information Modeling” is an innovative method to expand, develop and establish construction projects. This method uses *software* characteristics, it adds all important data to the construction how put example: graphic documentation; Construction Materials; price assessments and amount; geometric parameters of objects, among others. In addition to having new to form in if to work It is serve as aid for you professionals involved at the project (HEIFER *et al.*, 2019).

The term BIM was born in the United States in 1970 (SANTOS; PINTO, 2019), and has as a concept to be used in constructions that estimate the work interdisciplinary and/or multidisciplinary (BEZERRA *et al.*, 2019).

This one program it suits also as one tool for you professionals It is until clients related to the project/work. It evaluates and manages the correct means of implement in the building, always acting in the most correct way possible, following to the standards, Helping at the course It is looking for ever to preserve O maximum possible natural resources that are located in the same location as the building, and as a result ends up cooperating to increase the life cycle of

buildings and mitigate the use of matter cousin, damage It is waste (SAINTS; CHICK, 2019), being able to generate like this one economy in until 20% (CARVALHO; BRAGANÇA; MATEUS, 2017).

When using BIM, you also take advantage of its advantages, such as example: having better improvements in relation to improving quality in relationship to the information obtained, smaller cost at realization of project/work, adding employees and information management, and as mentioned above when using the BIM also ends up contributing to the reduction of the use of natural resources and how consequence results in collaboration for the sustainable increase of works and engineering projects and also results in a faster construction method, ensuring that the project is delivered before the scheduled date, or is delivered at the scheduled day, without delays (ZHANG, et al. al. 2019).

The use of BIM adds to the expansion of better quality throughout the project, helping to minimize errors through efficiency progress, accuracy, assessments It is communications. In consequence exist one better coordination between documents and the entire team, minimizing conflicts. All this progress is reflected in lower costs and shorter deadlines (CHEN; LUO, 2014). Second Bessoni (2018), BIM It is sustainability work good when implemented together, as it presents efficient proposals, helping to preserve the quite environment, having as goal one new mode in life, one new awareness general of the impact of development human in planet.

The most important contribution of BIM is in the acquisition of information to assist in the economy and the costs of general works on a building. In relationship The economy from the company for with O project, The technology BIM no provides no direct contribution, however indirectly, as it must be taken into account consideration that its application, when implemented correctly, helps in reducing costs indirectly, through other means, such as reduction in use in resources natural in excess and/or without need (OAK, 2009)

To the tools BIM for study in viability enlarge The I estimated in costs and the initial planning of projects that are still in the understanding or development phase. study in viability. As results, to the tools support at the time of decision in the first phases in project, entailing The I estimated preliminary in costs for start to constructions (BARISON, 2015).

Garcia (2014, p.184), further describes that “the usefulness to think about the cost before going into daydreams about the shape when thinking about in sustainability”, clarifying that sustainability in its economic pillar is necessary for the acceptance of an assertive formal decision and the search for the construction sustainable (GARCIA, 2014)

BIM allows projects to be carried out faster and more efficiently. safety, causing less waste, as it generates precise quantitative values, also assisting in a reliable calculation to

measure the duration of the work, and their correct equipment for use. These recommendations and the timelines that are proposed through this system, it helps a lot in reducing the negative impact on quite environment (GARCIA, 2014).

4 CONCLUSION

To the to spend of time, more engineers civilians It is Architects they are doing use from the modeling computational for perfect The efficiency of the projects It is seek better solutions to common problems in the works. The analysis of published works, explains the advancement of practice in recent years, as a result of of entanglement of the buildings It is of growth of the area in construction civil.

BIM is a technological means that brought innovation to the market, where it makes use of software covering all the information necessary to carry out a work. She brings with it numerous advantages and benefits, it is worth highlighting that when using this tool, will help to bring more collaboration on the part of the workers involved in the constructions, decreases like this The ticket in incorrect information and intrigues inside from the team.

The result of this work also showed the relationship between the BIM tool and the environment sustainable, fulfilling like this, O goal of work what he was to analyze The tool BIM applied to sustainability in construction of buildings.

However, when carrying out the research, the works found from the bibliographical survey highlights a development in the use of the methodology BIM It is in your miscellaneous possibilities, especially when the objective is to design It is put into practice the construction sustainable so much with less impact environmental how much at the sense from the economy It is management operational. AND worth highlighting what O use of BIM no it must be related as a method simple in adoption in one model of development, but it is a tool multidisciplinary what he has O intention for correlate It is potentialize you sectors complexes at design of projects in engineering sustainable.

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